

Consumer Satisfaction on Personal Care Products of Hindusthan Unilever Ltd (With Reference To Pollachi)

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Abstract

Now a day's most business organizations are operating in a complex and competitive environment where demands are constantly changing. In this era of intense competition, especially within the FMCG sector, one can achieve success only after having a thorough understanding about their target consumer preference and satisfaction. Personal care category in India was valued at Rs. 54.6 billion. An average Indian spends 8% of his income on personal care products. Personal care industry is composed of hair care, bath products, skin care and cosmetics, and oral care. Hindustan Unilever Limited (HUL) is India's largest Fast Moving Consumer Goods Company with a heritage of over 80 years in India and touches the lives of two out of three Indians. Hindustan Unilever is looking to diversify its beauty and personal care portfolio and is also working on expanding its distribution network across the country over the next two years. The study is conducted in and around Pollachi and a sample of 50 respondents was taken. The study intends to identify the level of satisfaction of various factors on the purchase of personal care products by the consumers. An attempt has been made to identify the preferred brand of personal care products of HUL. The study shows that consumers give more importance to the 'Price' of the personal care brands they buy. Further the variation of the influence of different factors across gender, marital status, age group and educational level of respondents was also analyzed in this article.

Keywords: FMCG - Preference - Customer Satisfaction – Brand – HUL – Personal care products.

INTRODUCTION

Fast Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) can be defined as packed goods that are consumed or sold at regular and small intervals. India's personal care industry is composed of hair care, bath products, skin care and cosmetics and oral care. The sector is driven by rising income, rapid urbanization and celebrity promotions. This industry accounts for 22% of the country's fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG), which is the term for Consumer Packaged Goods in India. The prices of the FMCG are relatively less and profits earned through such sales are more volume based. The FMCG Sector in India is the fourth largest sector in the Indian economy. As per the reports of the 2005-06 financial years, the market size of the sector was registered as USD 13.1 billion. The FMCG Sector in India involves a strict competition between the organized and unorganized sectors of consumer durables. The market size of the Indian FMCG Sector is expected to reach USD 33.4 billion by the year 2015. The consumption of health and personal care products in FMCG sector has increased in the recent past with rise in disposable income especially among the early stages group in India.

A few of the FMCG product are:

- Toiletries
- Soaps and detergents
- Cleaning and disinfecting agents
- Cosmetics
- Non-durables
- Pharmaceuticals

Further, the packaged food products and drinks are also sold under the FMCG, since these items are consumed or bought at regular intervals. Furthermore, recently the electronic items like mobile phones, MP3 players, external hard drives, etc, which has less life owing to its technological development, has also been brought under the gamut of FMCG sector.

Hindustan Unilever Limited (HUL) is an Indian consumer goods company based in Mumbai, Maharashtra. It is owned by Anglo-Dutch company Unilever which owns a 67.25% controlling share in HUL. HUL's products include foods, beverages, cleaning agents, personal care products and water purifiers. HUL was established in 1933 as Lever Brothers and in 1956, became known as Hindustan Lever Limited, as a result of a merger between Lever Brothers, Hindustan Vanaspati Mfg. Co. Ltd. and United Traders Ltd. It is

headquartered in Mumbai, India and employs over 18,000 workers, whilst also indirectly helping to facilitate the employment of over 65,000 people. The company was renamed in June 2007 as "Hindustan Unilever Limited". Hindustan Unilever's distribution covers over 2 million retail outlets across India directly and its products are available in over 6.4 million outlets in the country. A study by Nielsen, a market research firm, determined that shampoo is the most popular FMCG product in India. The \$818 million shampoo segment is dominated by Hindustan Unilever Ltd., owned by U.K.-based Unilever. Its most popular brands are Sunsilk, Clear, and Clinic Plus. Hair oil is another important product, valued at \$1.3 billion annually. India-based Marico's Parachute and Dabur are leaders in the production of branded coconut hair oil. Estimated at \$1 billion, the soap and bath category is significant. Soap is a prevalent product found in more than 90% of Indian households. The most common brands include Godrej's Cinthol, Reckitt Benckiser's Dettol, Wipro's Santoor, and Unilever's Lux, Dove, Hamam, and Lifebuoy.

Hindustan Unilever has three brands that are popular among Indian women—Fair & Lovely, Lakmé, and Ponds. Fair & Lovely was the world's first skin lightening cream and is the company's leading skin care brand. Colgate Palmolive's Charmis moisturizer is also prominent. Hindustan Unilever is another significant player with toothpaste brands Pepsodent and Close Up. As per research data, two out of three Indians use HUL products. The present study is an attempt to identify the preferred brand and the level of satisfaction on the Personal care products of HUL in Pollachi taluk.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The following are the main objectives of the study

- To identify the preferred brand of personal care products of Hindustan Unilever Limited.
- To study the factors influencing consumer satisfaction on the personal care products.
- To study the level of consumer satisfaction towards personal care products.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Gluckman (1986) studied the factors influencing consumption and preference for wine. The explicit factors identified were, the familiarity with brand name, the price of wine, quality or the mouth feel of the liquid, taste with regard to its sweetness or dryness and the suitability for all tastes. The implicit factors identified through extensive questioning were colour and appearance. The study conducted by **Kumar et al. (1987)** revealed that brand image is more important than the origin of the product, since the consumers were attracted by the brands.

Abrazhevich (2001) opines and confirms with his study that favorable image of product in the mind of customers has an important impact on purchase, which are showing more of the customer's interest in buying the product either it could be cosmetic products or personal care products. According to the study conducted by **Dr. Vinith Kumar Nair and Dr. Prakash Pillai (2007)** male consumers generally prefer to purchase and make the brand selection of cosmetics individually. Quality is the major factor influencing the purchase decision of male consumers. They tend to buy cosmetic items from a single shop of their convenience. It is also observed that male consumers buy all their cosmetic items from one shop. As **Fan Shean Cheng, Cheng Soon Ooi and Ding Hooi Ting (2010)** have observed that there is a significant and positive relationship between males concern towards self-image and their consumption of male grooming products.

Marketing strategies and customer satisfaction are important aspects for selling the product to achieve the highest sales level in the ponds skin care product. People are mostly satisfied with the overall quality of ponds and necessary advertisement should be made in order to increase the sales of ponds skin care product then the competitors **Jamuna(2013)**. The study done by **Ashok Yakkaldevi (2013)** reveals that the consumer behavior towards cosmetics apart from psychology and economics the role of history and tradition in shaping the Indian consumer behavior is quite unique. Consumers are also associated with values of care and affection. **Banu Rekha and Gokila (2015)** observed there exist a perfect positive correlation between the two factors. I.e. family income per month of the respondents and spend for herbal cosmetics product per month of the respondents. Majority of respondents, ranked first to quality of the product and there is a significant relationship between age and period of using the products.

DATA AND METHODOLOGY

The research design adopted in the study was descriptive in nature. The area of the study is in around Pollachi. The study is based on primary data collection. The data has been collected from the users of Personal care products. The secondary data was collected from the articles, journals, newspapers and various websites. The sampling technique used in this study is convenient sampling. A sample of 50 respondents were taken into account for the study. The statistical tools used for the study include, Percentage analysis, Mean and Chi-Square (χ^2) Test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**Demographic Profile of the Respondents**

Percentage analysis was used to analyze the data collected regarding socio-economic profile, average amount spend on personal care product each month, preferred place of purchase, sources of brand awareness, preference on the personal care products of the respondents. Table 1 summarizes the findings of socioeconomic profile of the respondents.

Table 1: Socio – Economic Profile of the Respondents

Parameters	Number of Respondents (N=50)	Percentage to Total
<u>Gender</u>		
Male	15	30
Female	35	70
<u>Age</u>		
20 – 30	37	74
31-40	09	18
Above 41	04	08
<u>Educational Qualification</u>		
Upto Higher Secondary	06	12
Under Graduation	15	30
Post Graduation	15	30
Professional	05	10
Other	09	18
<u>Marital Status</u>		
Married	22	44
Unmarried	28	56
<u>Number of Members In the family</u>		
Below 3	09	18
3-5	35	70
Above 5	06	12
<u>Occupation</u>		
Agriculture	07	14
Employee	14	28
Professional	02	04
Student	20	40
Home maker	07	14
<u>Monthly Family Income</u>		
Below Rs.10,000	13	26
Rs.10,001 – Rs.15000	23	46
Above Rs.15,000	14	28

Table 1 reveals that majority of the respondents are female (70%). Composition of age shows that the majority of the respondents are between the age group of 20-30 years (74%) and the monthly family income is between Rs.10, 001 – Rs.15000 (46%). Most of the respondents are private and public employee. Most of the respondents are unmarried (56%). Educational qualification of the majority of the respondents are Under graduates (30%) and post graduates (30%) .

Table 2: Average Amount Spend On Personal Care Product Each Month

Amount	Number of Respondents (N=50)	Percentage to Total
Rs 100 – Rs 500	31	62
Rs 501 – Rs 1000	15	30
Above Rs 1000	04	08

Table 2 discloses that majority of the respondents spend Rs 100 to Rs 500(62%) on purchase of personal care products monthly.

Table 3: Preferred Place of Purchase

Place of purchase	Number of Respondents (N=50)	Percentage to Total
Nearby Stores	15	30
Malls	05	10
Departmental Stores	30	60

Table 3 reveals that most of the respondents purchase their personal care products from the departmental stores (60%).

Table 4: Sources of Brand Awareness

Source	Number of Respondents (N=50)	Percentage to Total
Internet	09	18
Newspaper	03	06
Words of mouth	10	20
Television advertisement	28	56

Out of the 50 respondents 28 (56%) of the respondents source of awareness is television advertisement; 10(20%) of the respondents source of brand awareness is words of mouth; 3(6%) of the respondents source of brand awareness is newspaper; 9(18%) of the respondents source of brand awareness is Internet.

Table 5: Preference on the Personal Care Products of HUL

Brand/ Level of Preference	Most Preferred	Preferred	Less preferred
<u>Skin care</u>			
1.Ponds	19 (38%)	15 (30%)	16 (32%)
2.Fair & lovely	15 (30%)	23 (46%)	12 (24%)
3.Aviance	2 (4%)	6 (12%)	42 (84%)
4.Dove	14 (28%)	12 (24%)	24 (48%)
5.Vaseline	12 (24%)	15 (30%)	23 (46%)
6.Lakme	15 (30%)	11 (22%)	24 (48%)
<u>Hair care - shampoo</u>			
1.Sunsilk	12 (24%)	15 (30%)	23 (46%)
2.Dove	8 (16%)	20 (40%)	22 (44%)
3.Clear	13 (26%)	19 (38%)	18 (36%)
4.Clinic plus	19 (38%)	14 (28%)	17 (34%)
<u>Hair oil</u>			
Indhulekha	9 (18%)	9 (18%)	32 (64%)
<u>Soap/shower gels</u>			
1.Rexona	9 (18%)	13 (26%)	28 (56%)
2.Pears	15 (30%)	18 (36%)	17 (34%)
3.Dove	14 (28%)	17 (34%)	19 (38%)
4.Lux	9 (18%)	19 (38%)	22 (44%)
5.Liril	4 (08%)	7 (14%)	39 (78%)
6.Hamam	19 (38%)	14 (28%)	17 (34%)
7.Lifebuoy	20 (40%)	10 (20%)	20 (40%)
8.Breeze	4 (08%)	6 (12%)	40 (80%)
<u>Oral care</u>			
1.Pepsodent	15 (30%)	20 (40%)	15 (30%)
2.Close-up	19 (38%)	12 (24%)	19 (38%)

<u>Deodorants/perfumes</u>			
1.Axe	16 (32%)	12 (24%)	22 (44%)
2.Rexona	8 (16%)	20 (40%)	22 (44%)
<u>Herbal ayurvedic personal care</u>			
Ayush therapy	2 (04%)	7 (14%)	41 (82%)

Table 5 discloses that the respondents mostly prefer Ponds, fair & lovely and lakme in skin care brand; clear and clinic plus in hair care brand; Dove, Hamam, Lifebuoy in Soap brands; Close- up in oral care brands; Axe in deodorants.

Consumer Satisfaction on Personal Care Products of the respondents

Mean has been employed to ascertain the factors influencing the consumer satisfaction on the personal care products of HUL.

Table 6: Consumer Satisfaction on Personal Care Products

S.No	Factors	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
1.	Price	50	4.1600	0.548
2.	Availability	50	4.4400	0.674
3.	Brand Image	50	4.3000	0.677
4.	Promotional Offers	50	3.8000	0.880
5.	Advertisement	50	4.4400	0.643
6.	Quantity	50	4.1600	0.911
7.	Quality	50	3.9400	1.167
8.	Product education	50	3.6400	0.984
9.	Effectiveness	50	3.7400	0.899
10.	Product Feature	50	3.7200	1.069

Table 6 presents that most of the respondents are satisfied with respect to Price, Quantity, Advertisement, Availability and Brand image of the personal care products.

Demographic Variables Associated with Level of Satisfaction of the personal care products.

Chi-square test is employed to check whether there exists an association between the selected variables and the level of satisfaction on the personal care products of HUL. The findings given in Table 7 reveal that there is no significant association between the selected variables and level of satisfaction on the personal care products of HUL

Table 7: Level of satisfaction on the personal care products of HUL

Variables	χ^2	Table value	Df	Remarks
Gender	0.315	5.99	2	Not Significant*
Age	0.994	9.49	4	Not Significant*
Place of Purchase	0.527	9.49	4	Not Significant*

*At 5% level of significance

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

The study depends upon the primary data collected from the respondents in Pollachi. All sorts of limitation applicable to primary data are applicable to the present study too. Information as reported by respondents might be prejudiced. Respondents of Pollachi Taluk alone have been included in the sample. Hence, while generalizing the results, caution is to be exercised.

CONCLUSION

Fast moving consumer goods are essential for the people in their day to day life. Their importance is giving the personality oriented benefits to the consumers. The study reveals that Ponds, Fair & Lovely, Lakme, Clear, Dove, Hamam, Close-up and Axe are the preferred brands of personal care products. From the above analysis it is evident that the personal care products of Hindustan Unilever Limited provide satisfaction to the consumers in the way of Price, Quality and availability of the product. It is also observed that there is no significant association between the variables selected and the level of satisfaction of the consumers.

References

Journals

- Ashok Yakkaldevi (2013)“Consumer behavior among women with special reference to cosmetics” vol. 1(1) pp.1-5
- Banu Rekha.M and Gokila.K (2015)“A study on consumer awareness,attitude and preference towards herbal cosmetic products with special reference to Coimbatore city”, *International Journal of Interdisciplinary and Multidisciplinary Studies (IJIMS)*, Vol 2, No.4, pp 96-100
- Fan Shean Cheng, Cheng Soon Ooi, and Ding Hooi Ting (2010) *International Review of Business Research Papers*, Vol.6 (1), pp. 574 - 590
- Gluckman, L. Robert.,(1986), 'A consumer approach to branded wines', *European J. Mktg*, Vol 20 (6), pp21-31.
- Jamuna.Sand Nandhini.M(2013) a study on customer satisfaction towards ponds skin care product, *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, pp 19-22
- Kumar, K., Ambarish, Jordan, B.B. and Barker Tansu, A., (1987),'Made in India, what it means to Indian consumers?' *Ind. J. Mktg*, Vol 17 (9), pp26-34.
- Nagarajan.G and Dr.Khaja sheriff (2013) ‘Emerging challenges and prospects of fmcg product development in India’, *International Journal of Marketing, Financial Services & Management Research*,Vol.2, No. 1
- Dr. Vinith Kumar Nair and Dr. Prakash Pillai R (2007) ,“Marketing &Society” *International Marketing Conference , IIMK* pp 8-10

Books

- Abrazhevich, D., “Electronic payment systems: issues of user acceptance”, in Stanford-Smith,B. and Chiozza, E. (Eds), *E-Work and E-Commerce*, IOS Press, Amsterdam, 2001, pp 354-360.

Websites

- <http://www.amritt.com/industries/india-consumer-packaged-goods-market/personal-care/>
- https://www.fastmr.com/prod/1182146_hindustan_unilever_ltd_beauty.aspx
- <https://www.hul.co.in/about/who-we-are/introduction-to-hindustan-unilever/>
- www.wikipedia.com
- <http://www.top10listedcompaniesinindia.com/top-10-listed-personal-care-products-companies-in-india/>